

AN OVERVIEW OF THE IMPACT OF RENEWABLE ENERGY IN THE ARCHITECTURE OF ZERO ENERGY BUILDINGS

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Abstract:

Given that the world's irreversible energy sources have already been used up almost in their entirety and that fossil fuel prices are rising and that the building industry consumes 50% of all energy, a scarcity and waste in the energy sector are imminent. In order to meet the 12th century's energy demands, the concept of zero energy structures was developed. A balance between energy production and consumption is established in these buildings through the wise application of renewable technologies. Energy Zero Nearly Building is regarded as a comprehensive solution for lowering carbon dioxide emissions in the construction industry, saving energy, and maintaining the environment. One feature of the structure that should largely cut consumption Building energy should be taken into account. It has to do with architecture. Building architecture should be based on climatic circumstances and the potentials and constraints of climate should be taken into consideration in order to attain zero energy architectural design. In order to create an architecture that is based on and responsive to the climate, and as a result, a zero-energy architecture, the first step in zero energy design is to be aware of the climatic conditions and determine the potentials and possibilities of the climate of the location of the building. However, in order to build such a flexible and intelligent system with sustainable goals, all participating parties' planning, design, and implementation experts must be aware of their role in achieving the established shared goal and must work together to understand their part in achieving the predetermined common goal and the required performance. In this essay, we will first go through the definitions and background of zero energy buildings before looking at the approaches that can be taken to realize their objectives. Zero energy buildings have two main objectives: first, they strive to use as little energy as possible, and second, they use renewable energy sources to generate their own energy. Next, we'll look at several potential approaches to achieving these objectives.

Key Words: *Zero, Energy, Building, Architecture, Environment.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Commercial and residential buildings account for almost 40 percent of the primary energy used in the United States, Europe, and China [1-3]. In order to lessen the building's reliance on primary energy, energy storage technology has been studied. The usage of renewable energy, on the other hand, is a sensible way to conserve energy and reduce global warming and air pollution [4]. In Europe, commercial and residential buildings account for roughly 40% of primary energy consumption and 24% of greenhouse gas emissions [5].

In the graphs below, you can see the production of carbon dioxide gas, the amount of energy and also the amount of consumption in different sectors.

figure 1: The amount of carbon dioxide gas production in different sectors [source: 6].

Figure 2: The amount of energy consumed in different sectors [source: 7]

Utilizing renewable energy in buildings is one of the most pressing issues highlighted nowadays. In the next years, the challenge of maximizing and using renewable energy as an alternative to fossil fuels is to design buildings that not only fulfill their own energy demands, but also transmit extra energy to the urban facilities network. These structures are referred to as zero-energy buildings. Zero energy building or absolute zero energy (building energy zero net) is an umbrella term for structures with zero energy consumption or zero yearly carbon fuel usage. In the design of a zero-energy building, in addition to the standard considerations for conventional structures, additional particular considerations must be made. Since the energy used in this structure must be generated and supplied using all feasible techniques, increasing the building's energy consumption is equal to expanding its energy production capacity, if this is technically feasible. The plan's cost will hinder its implementation. The following concepts are considered in the design of zero-energy buildings as a result [8]:

2. HISTORY OF ZERO ENERGY BUILDINGS

Prior to World War II, research at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology on solar heating structures sparked an interest in lowering energy use. 1919 saw the beginning of the first building project including the installation of solar collectors and the usage of solar water heaters. 1944 might be regarded the year of progress towards the building of low-consumption, well-insulated homes [9].

3. DEFINITIONS AND TERMS OF ZERO ENERGY

The following are definitions of zero energy buildings (ZEB): The US Department of Energy (DOE) defines zero energy buildings as structures in which consumption and production of energy are balanced via the use of renewable technology. These structures aesthetically integrate the concepts of renewable energy architecture and satisfy the energy demands of the occupants [10]

A zero-energy building is one that is very energy-efficient, generates its own energy, and produces as much energy as it uses annually. The following points should be included in any definitions of zero-energy buildings:

- Zero energy building does not mean zero energy consumption.
- These structures are not independent of conveniences.
- The use of these structures does not result in energy rationing.
- The energy contained in these structures is not endless energy.

It is crucial to note that according to DOE's definition, a zero-energy building appears identical to a conventional structure [11].

The zero-energy building is a mix of art, energy-efficient building design, high-efficiency technology, and renewable energy generating technologies. There are numerous definitions for zero energy buildings and buildings with zero net energy consumption, with the majority of them considering solely energy use during the building's working hours and operation.

Globally, zero-energy buildings are still rare, most likely due to the unfamiliarity of the notion with the general public. Use as energy output meets demand, and a substantial reduction in energy consumption; energy prices equal zero or net zero greenhouse gas emissions.

these sorts of structures are also referred to by the following names [12]:

Zero energy building [13], zero energy emission building [13], virtually zero energy building [14], zero emission building [15], zero carbon building [16], zero net exergy building [17].

Andersen and his colleagues defined zero energy buildings (ZEB) as structures that produce no net greenhouse gas emissions [18] while being "economically feasible." Among the benefits of using this concept is the consideration of zero-emission energy [19].

In general, zero energy homes are those that are remote from the power system (not linked to the grid) and get their energy from renewable sources such as the sun and wind. What can be said about these residences? It is the supply of energy consumption on cloudy and rainy days that addressed this issue by conserving energy on other days. However, the expenses associated with energy storage are quite expensive, therefore the design of dwellings with zero net energy consumption is increasingly prevalent. It is that these homes interface with the network and, if necessary, buy energy from the network. Additionally, excess energy production is sold to the network at other times, and the yearly net energy consumption is zero (various time periods may be examined). If these homes produce more energy than they use annually, they are referred to be energy-palette [12].

The first concept of the zero-energy building was defined in such a manner that the act of getting energy from outside the building was forbidden and regarded a breach of the purpose. In practice, it was discovered that in order to achieve the defined objective, i.e. the absolute non-receipt of external energy, it is necessary to deprive the consumer of the use of certain household energy devices and equipment, or to incur substantial costs for the design and installation of new

energy producers. Moreover, the installation of solar panels (electricity generation) and solar collectors (heating) often needed more room than the structure itself. Therefore, the notion of isolating the energy of a structure from its surrounding interactions in order to retain the definition of zero energy in reality failed, and the term "near zero energy" was used in its stead. Net ZEB is: the executive notion of achieving a positive balance between the total energy received from outside the building plus the energy spent in the building with the total energy generated in the building [12].

4. BUILDING DESIGN WITH ZERO ENERGY

Energy crisis and the necessity of zero energy buildings with human progress and the industrialization of countries, the problem of air pollution has plagued the earth more than ever and according to reports, it has caused an increase in the temperature of the earth and a decrease in the thickness of the ozone layer. According to the published statistics from the urban planning and architecture information base, the total area of the buildings built on the ground is about one-sixth of the water areas.

The main design ideas for zero-energy buildings are centered on minimizing energy usage to the greatest extent feasible. The Canadian Zero Energy Homes Association provides two broad design concepts for these dwellings:

- Minimizing the building's energy use to the greatest extent practicable
- Renewable energy generation inside the building

Zero energy building technology: Zero energy buildings minimize energy consumption via the use of renewable technologies. The quantity and kind of these technologies used is not specified and relies on the type of structure. It is vital to note that these buildings use a variety of technologies and are not dependent on a single one. The following technologies are suggested for zero-energy buildings: [20].

In the tables below, you can see the two basic items that make up zero energy buildings, energy suppliers in zero energy buildings, as well as types of renewable energy and how they are used in zero energy buildings.

Table 1: items of energy suppliers in zero energy buildings in order of priority (source: author)

Supplier option in the direction of energy in zero energy buildings	Examples
Reduction of on-site energy consumption due to lack of biological building energy	Daylight, high efficiency, evaporative cooling, natural ventilation
Use of renewable and available energy at the entrance of the building	Solar water heater, installation of wind turbine, pv
Using renewable and available energy outside the site to produce energy in the building	Fertilizer produced from living sources with biomass, ethanol, wood pieces,
Using renewable and available energy outside the site to produce energy in the building	Solar water heater, water pressure reduction, turbine installation on site but not in the building

Table 2: types of renewable energy and how to use it in buildings (source: author)

Source type	Related item	Performance
Wind energy	Solar Water Heater	Air heating, hot water supply required
solar energy	Photovoltaic cell	Electricity supply Supplying ambient
Biofuel	Biogas	heating and heat required for cooking
	Bio fuel	Hot water supply, ambient heat
Ground heating	Ground heating pump (GSHP)	Ground heating
	Underfloor heating system	It has no construction use

5. ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN STRATEGIES

Introduction to Fundamentals and Accomplishments A zero energy building (ZEB) is, by definition, a residential or commercial structure that achieves a high degree of energy efficiency and is able to balance its energy demands via the use of technology and renewable energy. By employing this strategy towards the end of the 20th century, architects were able to create low-consumption buildings that fulfill their energy demands without relying on the energy network and return up to 25 m²/km of extra energy to the network annually. Explanation of these

objectives and how to define them is crucial to the design process [21]. The architectural component of the building should be studied in order to lower the energy consumption of buildings. To achieve zero energy architectural design, building architecture must be developed based on climatic circumstances, taking into account both the possibilities and constraints of climate. In order to create a zero-energy architecture, the first step in zero-energy design is to be aware of the climatic conditions and assess the potentials and possibilities of the environment of the building's site. The first stage in achieving a zero-energy architecture is a comprehensive climatic data study. Here, we provide several design concepts for zero-energy buildings [12].

5.1. The overall form should be as nearly square and rectangular as feasible, with at least corners and surrounding walls

In winter, the east/west orientation plan enhances the sun visor's surface area. Combining open floor layouts with cuts for cross ventilation, exhaust ventilation, or both is possible in permeable structures. (Cooling) Ventilation is a significant tool for cooling during hot seasons since it not only removes heat from the room, but also enhances the rate of evaporation, which makes inhabitants feel colder. Air circulation during the day in hot regions and at night in cold ones. Cross-ventilation is an essential supplementary method in any case, since moderate is often silent.

5.2. Positioning the most windows on the south face and the fewest on the north face

Illumination is a function of the distance to the window, the height of the window from the floor of the room, the window's size, and the wall's reflecting coefficient. The greater the distance from the window wall, the less access there is to natural light. Consequently, the building's breadth is a decisive factor for the usage of natural sunlight. When the wind blows around the structure, the impact of solar heating and cross ventilation (heating and cooling) is amplified in rooms that face the sun and the wind.

5.3 Minimum external opening count [22]

5.4. **The form of roofs:** roofs should be sufficiently sized, oriented, and sloped so that solar hot water systems may use the sun [Figure 4].

Figure 4: Terry's house - New Mexico - America [source: 12]

5.5. Solar spaces and greenhouses:

The purpose of solar spaces and greenhouses is to store and transport solar heat to adjacent rooms [23].

Figure 5: Balkom greenhouse space [source: 23]

Figure 6: a view of the solar greenhouse [source: 12]

5.6. Walls and roofs that absorb heat retain the sun's heat in an air layer and transmit it to the building structure.

5.7. Double-walled materials may reflect sunlight and limit heat transmission to the interior layers (cooling).

5.8. thermal storage walls may gather and store the sun's heat:

Indirect solar absorption systems, including Trombe walls and blue walls, position a thermal mass between the compartment to be heated and the southern façade. Therefore, unlike direct absorption systems, these systems do not allow sunlight to enter the space. Through the glass surfaces, sunlight warms the storage wall, which in turn warms the area. The quantity of heat that goes through a wall is dependent on its composition and thickness. Masonry walls let heat transfer from the sunny side to the inside of a room. The delay will be a few hours. Blue storage walls transmit heat more quickly because they operate mostly through displacement.

5.9. Materials and insulation used in the building's walls:

an illustration of insulation in zero-energy structures. Consider installing a minimum of 30 cm of thermal insulation A type of insulation panel called SID, this panel consists of a foam sheet placed between two wood sheets and is used in walls and ceilings [25]. The organization and structure

of these buildings is such that it is possible to remove mechanical systems, in this project the living and working spaces are separated [25-26].

Figure 7: How to insulate in zero energy buildings [source: 24].

Figure 8: a type of insulation panel in zero energy buildings [source: 24].

5.10. Blue roofs provide both heating and cooling capacities:

And it is particularly useful in regions with bright sky in low latitudes. It is typically composed of water bags with a depth of 15 to 20 centimeters that are set on a flat metal deck. Its bottom surface conforms to the shape of the roof, while its top side is insulated with a removable material [12]. The movable insulation is covered [12].

Figure 9: How blue roofs work at night and day in summer and winter [source: 12].

5.11. Photo voltaic ell:

The orientation of solar walls and roofs should be such that they absorb sunlight and are able to provide the building's electrical demand (Electricity) [27].

Figure 10: Combined use of wind caps and photovoltaics [source: 28]

6. ADVANTAGE OF ZERO ENERGY BUILDING:

- Compatible with nature
- Energy consumption balance with energy demand
- Maximum use of Passive Energy
- Decreasing energy demand
- Reducing electricity consumption
- Elimination of redundant energy-consuming systems
- Just Sufficient Design
- Significant reduction of environmental degradation
- Zero fossil fuel
- 100% use of renewable energies
- zero heating of buildings
- Heating through inactive systems
- 11% reduction in drinking water consumption
- Use of ventilation system without mechanical devices
- Optimum use of wood waste and biofuel production
- easy maintenance [29].

7. DISADVANTAGE OF USING NON-RENEWABLE RESOURCE SYSTEMS:

7.1. Start-up costs: The most important problem with these systems is their high installation and setup costs. Indeed, these systems will be cost-effective in the long run.

7.2. Dependence on the intensity of sunlight: According to the need of these systems for sunlight, atmospheric changes are effective on the amount of energy produced in these systems. is to pay attention to this issue in the design of systems.

7.3. The need for energy storage: In most cases, it is necessary to use batteries for energy storage, which causes an increase in costs.

7.4. People's lack of familiarity with the photovoltaic system: Due to the novelty of using photovoltaic technology in buildings, only a part of people is familiar with its facilities and values. The subject has a negative effect on the development of its market [27].

8. CONCLUSION

In recent years, a great deal of effort has been devoted to the use of renewable energies, and the large-scale generation of energy from these sources via the use of cutting-edge technology has become essential and vital. Is. On the other side, understanding how to use renewable energy in buildings is crucial, particularly in modern design. These buildings with modern technologies include zero-energy structures. The architecture of the building should be created in accordance with the climatic circumstances, taking into account the potentials and limits of the environment. The primary objective of zero energy buildings is to decrease the building's energy consumption to the lowest level achievable, while the second objective is to create electricity from renewable sources. This article strives to address the problem of building energy in the earliest phases of architectural design, to discover the ideal shape of a tall structure for collecting solar energy, and to identify a feature that effectively reduces a tall building's energy consumption. In this study, the reduction of energy consumption in the building through the use of passive solutions to reduce energy consumption with high economic justification and the achievement of a logical balance, in accordance with the definitions of zero energy, between the amount of energy consumed and its production through resources is of primary importance. Renewable energy and electricity grid are involved.

References

- [1] Sh. Pless, P. Torcellini , Getting to Net Zero, ASHRAE Journal 2443, 51, 18, (2016).
- [2] N. Aste, R. Adhikari,C. Pero, "Photovoltaic Technology for Renewable Electricity Production: Towards Net Zero Energy Buildings," in Clean Electrical Power (ICCEP), International Conference on, ed: IEEE, 446-450, (2011).
- [3] Li. J. Colombier, M. Managing Carbon Emissions in China through Building Energy Efficiency, Journal of Environmental Management,2436-2447, (2009).
- [4] M. Z, Jacobson, Review of Solutions to Global Warming, Air Pollution, and Energy Security, Energy & Environmental Science, second volume, 148- 173, (2009).
- [5] B. Belussi, A.Barozzi, L. Danza, A. Devitofrancesco, C. Fanciulli, M. Ghellere, G. Guazzi, I. Meroni, F. Salamone, F. Scamoni, C. Scrosati, A review of performance of zero energy buildings and energy efficiency solutions, J. Build. Eng. ,(2019).
- [6] K.Ahmed Ali, M.I. Ahmad, Y. Yusup, Issues, impacts, and mitigations of carbon dioxide emissions in the building sector, Sustainability 12 ,(2020).
- [7] Eurostat, Final energy consumption by sector,available at: <http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/page/portal/statistics/search_database>, (2014).
- [8] Bed ZED, and beyond, International Institute for Environment and Development. Volume. 21(2): 527–544.
- [9] J. Wali Elahi, A. Moti Birjandi A look at clean energy and environmentally friendly structures in the design of cities and buildings, (2011).
- [10] P. Hernandez, Kenny.P; 318, (2010).
- [11] G. Cherkzai, M. Farrokhzad, H. Saalarian, Building design with zero energy,
- [12] EU, Directive 2009/28/EU, European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources and amending and subsequently repealing Directives 2001/77/EC and 2003/30/EC.
- [13] EC, Guidelines accompanying Commission Delegated Regulation (EU), no. 244/2012 of 16 January ,supplementing Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on the energy performance of buildings by establishing a comparative methodology framework for calculating costoptimal levels of minimum energy performance requirements for buildings and building elements, Official Journal of the European Commission, available: <[http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52012XC0419\(02\)](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52012XC0419(02))> (19.04.2012).
- [14] Ecofys, cost-effective climate protection in the EU Building stock, report for EURIMA, (2005).
- [15] EC, Commission staff working document—on a new approach to the European Programme for Critical Infrastructure Protection—making European Critical Infrastructures more secure, SWD, p.18 (318 final), (2013).
- [16] H. Lund, A. Marszal, P. Heiselberg, Zero Energy Buildings and mismatch compensation factors, Energy Build. 43 (7) (2011) 1646–1654. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild>, (2011).

- [17] Entranze, cross-analysis on Member States plans to develop their building regulations towards the nZeb standard, 2013, pp. 1–256, available; [http://www.entranze.eu/files/downloads/D5_1_3/ENTRANZE Integration of report D5.1 D5.2 D5.3 final.pdf](http://www.entranze.eu/files/downloads/D5_1_3/ENTRANZE_Integration_of_report_D5.1_D5.2_D5.3_final.pdf).
- [18] EC, consolidated information from the Member States on Nearly Zero Energy Buildings, available http://ec.europa.eu/energy/efficiency/buildings/implementation_en.htm, (2014)
- [19] www.daviddarling.info
- [20] P. Torcellini, S. Pless, and M. Deru, Zero, Energy Buildings A Critical Look at the Definition: ‘ Pacific Grove, California, Available at: <http://zeroenergyhouse.co.nz/lighting>, August 14–18, (2006).
- [21] www.Zeh.com
- [22] <http://www.york.ac.uk>
- [23] P. Hernandez, P. Kenny, from net energy to zero energy buildings: Defining life cycle zero energy buildings.(LC-ZEB).Energy and Buildings,42,.815-821, (2010).
- [24] Deng, S., Dalibard, A., and Martin, M. Energy supply concepts for zero energy residential buildings in humid and dry climate. Energy conversion and Management, 52, 2455-2460, (2011).
- [25] <http://www.bedzedhouse.co.uk>
- [26] S. Deng, A. Dalibard, M.Martin, Y.J.Dai, U.Eicker, R.Z.Wang ,Energy Conversion and Management (2011
- [27] H. Jajarmi, B. Behnia, T. Mozafari, A. Koushki, The use of renewable natural energies in building architecture